

Impact of Globalization on Business Practices

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Abstract

Globalisation, or the globalisation of businesses and societies, has made it possible to transfer money, goods, services, and technology across international borders. One of its earliest forms is the Silk Road, which dates back to the era of prehistoric trade networks. The Age of Discovery began in the fifteenth century, and with it came the beginning of global trade and the Industrial Revolution. Promoting trade and cooperation as well as the exchange of resources, concepts, and knowledge all depend on globalization. This research paper investigates its effects on the Indian economy and the global economy using secondary sources and data relevant to politics, economics, and society. Technological, communication, and transportation advancements have sped up globalisation, changing customs, economies, and cross-cultural interactions. This has affected society's way of life and encouraged instability or larger social safety nets. The Indian economy has been supported by international markets, foreign investment, and cross-cultural exchange, especially in the travel and tourism sector. As multinational corporations (MNCs) promote global trade, governments must prioritise social justice. Companies and governments are able to adjust to and reap the benefits of globalisation thanks to trade opportunities, new markets, efficiency, and competitiveness brought about by economic expansion. Economic development is impacted by globalisation, which causes industry decline, job losses, income inequality, and environmental damage. For sustainable growth, businesses and governments need to fund education, invest in SMEs, and diversify. Indian agriculture, culture, identity, and education are all impacted by globalisation. Despite the foregoing, the primary goal of this research article is to use secondary sources of information and relevant statistical data to conduct a macroeconomic theoretical analysis of the effects of globalisation on the world economy, the Indian economy, and other issues.

Key words: Globalisation, Economic Development, Multinational corporations (MNCs)

Introduction

The process of international integration of goods, technology, capital, information, and cultures is known as globalisation. Growing interdependence amongst nations and increased social and economic openness are its defining characteristics. The political, social, and economic systems of many nations increasingly freely interact with one another as globalisation advances and change to foster even more interaction. The business philosophy known as "globalisation of business" entails looking at one's company from a global perspective, employing technology that is feasible on a global scale, providing goods and services that are better suited to meet the needs of customers in a global setting, upholding a standard of quality in accordance with international standards, developing a global corporate citizenship identity, and, in the end, cultivating a global organisational and business culture. "The growing economic interdependence of countries worldwide through increasing volume and variety of cross-border transactions in goods and services, free international capital flows, and

more rapid and widespread diffusion of technology" is how the International Monetary Fund defines globalisation.

Globalisation involves:

- The opening up of trade that allows goods and services to travel across the world more freely.
- An increase in foreign investment –companies investing overseas by building plants, contracting subsidiaries or buying stock in foreign countries.
- The opening up of capital markets which increases the flow of money across the world.
- Improved access to communication—from the development of new technology like the internet to cheaper plane tickets.

Globalization is caused by four fundamental forms of capital movement throughout the global economy. The four important capital flows are:

- Human Capital (i.e. Immigration, Migration, Emigration, Deportation, etc.)
- Financial Capital (i.e. Aid, Equity, Debt, Credit & Lending, etc.)
- Resource Capital (i.e. Energy, Metals, Minerals, Lumber, etc.)
- Power Capital (i.e. Security Forces, Alliances, Armed Forces, etc.)

The Impact of Globalization on World Economy

Increased competition from globalisation leads to more affordable, higher-quality goods and services. This competition helps consumers by promoting better products and more foreign direct investment. Globalisation has increased competition, which has led to a flourishing of technical innovation and foreign direct investment, boosting economic output through efficient processes. Economists claim that increased market efficiency, increased competitiveness, and quicker wealth creation are some advantages of globalisation. As globalisation offers both short- and long-term benefits that are essential for economic success, it is a good thing for individuals, companies, governments, and organisations. Globalisation has been a long-standing phenomenon since human migration. But thanks to advancements in technology, it has expanded swiftly, impacting both the global economy and modern living. Because of this quick growth, globalisation has evolved into a worldwide achievement. Technological, political, and environmental developments are supporting the expansion of global corporate activities. China's 36% shoe and clothing production share with the US, compared to 4% in the US, has a significant effect on the world economy. Through promoting free trade, accelerating economic development in developing countries, and easing the transfer of knowledge and technology, globalisation benefits the world economy. It also makes it possible to manage expenses, localise content, and fund research and development. A few of the detrimental effects of globalisation on the world economy include job threats, the production of harmful goods by developing countries, issues with product quality, cultural differences, and adjustments to foreign exchange, rules, and regulations that influence globalization's goals.

The Contribution of Multinational Corporations (MNCs) in Globalization:

As demonstrated by past initiatives like the Silk Road, globalization—an expedited form of economic integration—has boosted trade between countries, enhanced communication, and increased the number of interconnected nations. The benefits of globalisation to the Indian economy include increased foreign investment, a boost to intercultural dialogue, the opening up of new markets for foreign goods, a promotion of competition, and easier access to cutting-edge technology. This has the effect of increasing output, improving efficiency, and lowering costs, especially in the travel and tourism industry. It also improves the standard and efficiency of local industries. Increased cross-border movement of people, goods, capital, data, and ideas is leading to an increase in international trade and investment. Through the transformation of agriculture and other economic sectors, it unites national economies with the global economy. But it can also have a negative impact on Indian agriculture because foreign companies can enter the market with ease and affect farmers' margins. Globalisation has helped the growth of agricultural products in spite of these obstacles. Because they

manufacture their products abroad in addition to selling them there, multinational corporations (MNCs) are crucial to the globalisation process. Due to their ability to combine markets, attract investments, and facilitate cross-border trade, MNCs significantly accelerate globalisation. Global ties are strengthened as a result, which helps consumers – rich urban consumers in particular – who now have more options and can access better products at lower prices. Small parts of the production process are dispersed globally. The convergence of global business and development leads to the dispersion of resources, goods, services, and technology. By collaborating with regional and small producers, integrating markets, and promoting investment and international trade in goods, multinational corporations (MNCs) significantly contribute to globalisation. Globalisation is accelerated by MNCs, who locate their production facilities in areas with cheap labour, readily available markets, and stable political environments. More competition benefits consumers, draws more capital to India, and fosters the growth of regional companies in the raw material supply.

Globalization and the Industrial Revolution:

The free flow of goods, services, and wealth has been made possible by economic policy and technology; a political study examines historical changes in the significance of globalisation. Throughout the Industrial Revolution, steamships, railroads, and technological advancements promoted faster trade, which increased demand for textiles, iron, and manufactured goods on a worldwide scale.

Effect of Globalization on Indian Education:

With the support of government initiatives like the New Education Policy, the Indian educational system embraces globalisation and information technology, promoting new tools like e-learning, flexible learning, distant education, and overseas training.

Global Market:

Because globalisation enables countries to manufacture and sell goods in their own markets, those countries gain from it. Certain developed nations charge more, while others demand more raw materials. Coordination fosters the production of low-cost, profitable goods while supporting low-paid locals and giving non-industrialized nations access to reasonably priced goods.

Surplus of Employment Opportunities:

Export growth, the relaxation of capital restrictions, and cross-cultural management have greatly improved employee benefits and lifted many out of extreme poverty. Every nation has a unique culture that shapes how people act and are received. It is challenging to unite societies to form a global one because of differences in laws, gender norms, and educational systems. Nonetheless, a lot of countries have adopted American cultural elements—like competition and time management—into their business processes. Cross-functional interaction is made possible by competition, which lowers costs and improves labour and output quality. It stimulates development and communication by luring individuals to look for reasonably priced raw material sources. 90% of individuals earn money from their jobs.

Indian Economy:

Future Challenges Sustaining the growth momentum and achieving an annual average growth of 9-10% in the next five years. Simplifying procedures and relaxing entry barriers for business activities and Providing investor friendly laws and tax system. Checking the growth of population; India is the second highest populated country in the world after China. However, in terms of density India exceeds China as India's land area is almost half of China's total land. Due to a high population growth, GNI per capita remains very poor. It was only \$ 2880 in 2003 (World Bank figures). Boosting agricultural growth through diversification and development of agro processing. Expanding industry fast, by at least 10% per year to integrate not only the surplus labour in agriculture but also the unprecedented number of women and teenagers joining the labour force every year. Developing world-class infrastructure for sustaining growth in all the sectors of the economy Allowing foreign

investment in more areas. Effecting fiscal consolidation and eliminating the revenue deficit through revenue enhancement an expenditure management. Some regard globalization as the spread of western culture and influence at the expense of local culture. Protecting domestic culture is also a challenge. Global corporations are responsible for global warming, the depletion of natural resources, and the production of harmful chemicals and the destruction of organic agriculture. The government should reduce its budget deficit through proper pricing mechanisms and better direction of subsidies. It should develop infrastructure with what Finance Minister P Chidambaram of India called “ruthless efficiency” and reduce bureaucracy by streamlining government procedures to make them more transparent and effective. Empowering the population through universal education and health care, India must maximize the benefits of its youthful demographics and turn itself into the knowledge hub of the world though the application of information and communications technology (ICT) in all aspects of Indian life although, the government is committed to furthering economic reforms a developing basic infrastructure to improve lives of the rural poor and boost economic performance. Government had reduced its controls on foreign trade and investment in some areas.

Conclusion:

Globalisation has an impact on economic development, leading to employment losses, dwindling industries, income inequality, and environmental degradation. Governments and businesses are investing in education, diversifying their industries, and funding SMEs. As competition and innovation have increased in the financial, industrial, and agricultural sectors, the outsourcing industry in India has grown. A comprehensive plan is necessary for equitable growth and sustainable development. There are conflicting effects of globalisation on society, particularly in the areas of the economy, agriculture, and ecology. A more equal global economy has been brought about by advances in technology, increased trade, and cross-cultural exchanges. It also bears obligations such as unequal income sharing and wealth distribution. Globalisation has affected Indian agriculture, leading to high financial returns, changes in the rural social structure, resource extraction, and forced labour. It has also led to increased emissions, global warming, air pollution, deforestation, and pollution. It has influenced culture, identity, and education in addition to talks about how markets and communication function. Globalisation widens the wealth gap because of underpayment of experts and charity favouritism. The pandemic upsets global patterns, but supply chain laws and technological advancements can reshape trade. In order to halt epidemics and encourage recovery, businesses need to view globalisation as a key factor in the future.

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